

THE IMPORTANCE OF MOTIVATION IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: English language education's "neglected heart" has been described as motivation. Some teachers may need to pay more attention to the fact that all learning activities are filtered via the students' motivation. In this way, students direct the flow of the classroom. There is no pulse; there is no life in the classroom if students are not motivated. Teachers who learn to use direct techniques to boost student motivation in their classrooms may become happier and more successful educators. The question of motivation is critical, particularly in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) contexts. Other aspects of teaching methodology appear to pale in comparison. Because of the harsh reality of learning English for most foreign language learners and students, it is critical to consider motivation as the essence of English language instruction.

Key words: Self-regulation; Motivation; Global Self-identity; Foreign Languages; Intrinsic Motivation; Extrinsic Motivation

Introduction. Motivation is one of the most crucial aspects of foreign language learning. It is seen as a significant contributor to linguistic results, which usually encompass the knowledge structure of the language, including vocabulary, pronunciation, grammar, and the four basic abilities of the language. Factors contributing to a foreign language learner's success are how the foreign language situations are structured (Anjomshoa & Sadighi, 2015). Because of these challenging circumstances, foreign language learners must be highly motivated to succeed in learning English. There needs to be more English input in the environment, and there needs to be more possibilities for engagement with English speakers. There need to be

stronger role models supporting English learning, and there may need to be widespread social acceptance of proficiency in English. Every teacher's dream is to have motivated students who are willing to work hard, add their own aims to those of the classroom, concentrate their efforts on the tasks at hand, stay strong through challenges, do not require constant encouragement, and may even stimulate others in the classroom, promoting collaborative learning. However, all know that the motivation for students' learning varies significantly, ebbs and flows over the course of the year and comes from a variety of sources, both internal to the learner and external to the learner. We can generally identify who is motivated and who is not as teachers, and we may question how, or even if, we can absorb the motivation of some and transfer it to others.

Methodology of analysis

The method concept analysis, which analyzes concepts through theoretical analysis, was employed in this work as a qualitative approach. The research data was gathered through a review of the literature on numerous theoretical publications, such as articles and books.

Definition of Motivation

The term motivation has several different definitions. To be motivated, the learner must have something to look forward to, that is relevant to the goal or target. This goal would be to study a foreign language. There needs to be something the student intends to achieve or gain, with the target language serving as the means to accomplish that goal. The learner's motivation for learning another language might range from gaining success, meeting others' expectations, or purchasing a new car to having a better job because of knowledge of the chosen language. Some argue that motivation empowers people and offers direction.

Factors Influencing Motivation

Many individuals believe that there is a link between personality traits and successful foreign language learning. Unsuccessful learners are often regarded as lacking self-confidence, quiet, reluctant to share their ideas, and apprehensive. Successful learners, on the other hand, may exhibit a variety of qualities such as extrovert, self-confidence, active, passive, independent, introverted, or shy. Learners who try to adopt a more flexible attitude toward learning a foreign language have a better probability of success than those whose affective filters are continually activated. In such a case, a warm and encouraging environment could be decisive. However, the judgment of classmates can be detrimental, eroding confidence in one's

potential to succeed. It may impede or distract the learner from attending to and remembering new items when combined with a broad dread of negative evaluation. People who have acquired helplessness believe they have no control over their actions and believe intelligence is unchanging and failure is primarily attributable to a lack of ability. Finally, learners' resistance can be caused by internal and external circumstances, which are tied to their skill or inability to solve difficulties in the past. Individual learners' sense of competence and self-efficacy are also essential factors influencing learning motivation. They are frequently eager to take risks, are not frightened of making language blunders, and are willing to acquire some of the identifying qualities of another cultural group. Their affective filter is minimal, and they can comprehend much of the understandable input provided to them. Such people, sometimes referred to as mastery oriented, view failure as a lack of effort and work towards improving their subsequent performance.

Intrinsic Motivation and Extrinsic Motivation

Paying attention to the importance of motivation in the teaching process and establishing, reinforcing, and increasing it, can be an effective and beneficial aspect in the process of language learning. In reality, teachers' understanding of student attitudes and their relationship to the teaching process gives a framework within which language teachers might employ more useful and effective methods. In a brief, motivation is a physical, psychological, or social need that inspires an individual to accomplish or achieve his objective, fulfill his need, and, lastly, feel fulfilled as a result of completing his goal. We can conclude that the amount, range, and type of incentive all play a significant and determining role in the process of learning. Furthermore, the language teacher motivates learners to learn a language. According to researchers, motivation is divided into two categories: internal incentive and extrinsic motivation. In general, two types of motivation may be observed among learners: high attitude, which has a good, efficient, and helpful influence, and low attitude, which creates barriers and causes weakness in language acquisition.

Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations are essential variables in learners' success at all stages of learners education. Every learner is driven differently, and it takes time and effort to get them excited about learning, working hard, and pushing themselves to improve. Learners, teachers, and parents play critical roles in providing and fostering motivation in the teaching and learning environments. Intrinsic motivation is the enthusiasm and interest in doing and participating in certain activities because an individual finds them appealing and pleasurable. In other words, Intrinsic motivation is the desire to engage in an activity for its own sake. Intrinsically driven individuals

participate in and practice activities and tasks because they find them enjoyable. Intrinsically motivated students are more likely to persevere with complex challenges and learn from their errors and mistakes. Furthermore, intrinsic motivation is vital and fundamental for the integration process, which involves the assimilation or mixing aspects of one's general internal awareness and knowledge with new understanding.

Researchers believe that Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, is the desire to participate in activities for unrelated reasons to the activity. These motivations include anticipating a reward or punishment, such as passing an exam or receiving a high grade. In other words, we can say Extrinsic motivation is motivation to perform a task or activity as a means or method of achieving a goal. Providing educational and academic benefits to students, encouraging them, and asking simple and straightforward questions at the start of class before asking tough questions help enhance enthusiasm for studying (Walker, Greene, & Mansell, 2006; Ng & Ng, 2015). Both internal and extrinsic motives have two subgroups that can be activated in the learner. The intrinsic motivation of an extroverted learner is such that the learner benefits from and feels satisfied by communicating with others. In contrast, the intrinsic motivation of an introverted learner is such that the learner uses language for meditation and personal thinking in addition to personal activities and affairs. Indeed, relying on intrinsic and extrinsic motives, the instructor should make the classroom peaceful and anxiety-free to create and develop either.

Attitudes and Motivation

Variables in second language acquisition are determined by the amount of understandable input received and understood by the acquirer, as well as the intensity of the affective filter. Most people feel that attitudes and motivation are closely related to language learning performance. This may explain why some people learn languages far more easily than others; in the same classroom setting, some pupils improve quickly, while others struggle and never achieve command of a second language. When external pressure is the only incentive for learning a second language, internal motivation may be weak, and attitudes toward learning are likely to be negative. Learners will be more attentive in class if they have positive attitudes regarding the foreign language, its speakers, the teacher, and the course. They would also take examinations more seriously and, to achieve more, seek out circumstances in which they might gain further practice in the foreign language. Some critics distinguish between attitudes based on environmental circumstances or subject qualities such as age or gender. Thus, we can differentiate between perspectives centered on the educational components of second language learning (educational attitudes) and social

attitudes centered on the cultural consequences of second language acquisition. Gender differences are also assumed to influence attitudes and motivation: experience shows that girls have much more favorable views toward learning languages than boys, with the vast number in the faculties of philology and foreign languages serving as an example. Even though many experts do not believe in an absolute biological basis for learning, there are instances where age variations may have a significant impact on foreign language learning. The concept that young children learn foreign languages faster than older learners is clearly disputed by evidence of areas where the latter do better. However, adults' emphatic capability, openness to engage in actual communication, and ego permeability may be weaker, mainly due to external circumstances.

Discussion and conclusion. The preceding discussion demonstrates that motivation is a critical and successful aspect of language learning. Therefore, language instructors and lecturers must find, recognize, and pay more attention to their students' personalities. Furthermore, they should be aware of motivation, its significance, and its various forms. They should also recognize and become acquainted with each student's character and personality. Following that, they should identify and recognize the type of motivation associated with that personality type and incorporate it into their teaching method. In these circumstances, they can benefit from a practical, helpful, and effective language classroom and a positive outcome in their teaching. Motivation is a unique human construct that has long confounded those who have attempted to comprehend and explain it. Moreover, everyone's incentive to learn is fluid rather than fixed. As teachers, they can have a direct impact students motivation to study a foreign language.

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